

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

COORDINATION AND SUPPORT ACTION

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: CTA

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report – Spain

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of the Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA) for the organisation and validation of the Agroecological market of San Jerónimo event in Seville (Andalusia), Spain on 01/28/2023. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Agroecological market of San Jerónimo event in Seville (Andalusia), Spain.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

The selected “Let’s meet” event concept in Andalusia has been the **Producer Event**, which was held on **January 28th, 2023** at the **Agroecological Market of San Jerónimo (Seville)**. SFSC is a unique way to reconnect food consumers and producers by providing fresh and high-quality products, with competitive prices. In the organised event, customers understood and experienced the holistic quality of local food, and some of the practical challenges to move to a more direct business relationship. Producers met consumers and showed them what they offer at an informal event, as well as consumers learned the importance of buying local products, and found out how and where they buy these products. A series of specialized local producers were present so consumers could try, buy, and learn about their products.

Two local producers participated in this event: Caña Nature and Conservas Artesanales Contigo. On the one hand, **Caña Nature** showed products such as natural tomato, avocado and gazpacho, and on the other hand, **Conservas Artesanales Contigo** showed vegan sobrasada, different organic jams (with and without sugar) and vegan pates. This event has allowed local producers to explain directly to consumers the quality of the products and different points of sale.

In addition to the producer-consumer interaction, some producer-producer meetings took place. Some small local producers participated in this ecological market, who have been able to learn about the agroBRIDGES project, how they can benefit, and an interesting exchange of ideas took place.

The following table shows the event programme:

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Presentation of the event to the participants	Arrival on the market and introduction of the project to the other producers and market participants	9:00 – 9:30	Agroecological market Huerto San Jerónimo Sevilla
Assembly of the space	Reception of the producers, assembly of the structure and preparation of the products	9:30 – 11:00	Agroecological market Huerto San Jerónimo Sevilla
Product test	Test local products to different market consumers and explanation of the	11:00 – 17:00	Agroecological market Huerto San Jerónimo

	agroBRIDGES project and the importance of consuming local products		Sevilla
Product raffle	Raffle for a basket with some of the products among consumers	13:30	Agroecological market Huerto San Jerónimo Sevilla
Dismantling and collection	Collection of products and dismantling of the stand	17:00 – 17:30	Agroecological market Huerto San Jerónimo Sevilla

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The event was held in the San Jerónimo Agroecological Market, in an area of social gardens in the San Jerónimo neighbourhood, in Seville, carried out monthly, located next to the Alamillo park and near to the Guadalquivir River. Due to the widespread interest in this market locally in the city and after a survey of possible markets in the surrounding area, it was decided to participate in the January market.

At first, a series of meetings were held with the organizers of the market, to introduce the project, the objective of our participation, the suitability of the event and the benefits that could be obtained from a networking and visibility point of view at different levels. Once the common interests had been clarified in mid-December, the date of the event was set, and the first steps were taken.

To participate in this market, the variety of products already on the market has been considered, in order to avoid repeating products, and to offer new possibilities and varieties to consumers. On this basis, two producers were selected within the agroBRIDGES MAP members who fulfilled all preliminary requirements and offered organic products that are not yet sold on the market.

Figure 1: Assembly of the structure

Figure 2: Assembly of the structure

Figure 3: Producer Event

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For the organization of the event, a distinction has been made between CTA staff and the external team of collaborating producers:

Within CTA, four people have participated in the organization. On the one hand, two of them have focused on communication: dissemination on social networks (LinkedIn, Twitter, website, writing an article), preparation of informative brochures about the event, the products, the producers and about the agroBRIDGES project in general, roll-up design, transport of the material, and in addition, they have also been physically at the event to prepare the post-event dissemination material. Other two persons have been mainly in charge of contact with the producers and the organizers of the event, they have designed the event programme, coordinating all the activities, interacting with the public during the event, among other activities.

The external personnel, which had a fundamental role in this event, have been the two producers, Caña Nature and Conservas Artesanales Contigo, who have prepared and brought their products and dissemination material, and have been in direct contact with consumers giving detailed information about their products, origin, type of cultivation, preparation, advantages over non-local products and the different points of sale. In addition, they have been exchanging ideas about their business models with the other producers.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Communication officer	4	Development of promotional material, diffusion in social networks, presence at the event, material purchase, contact with consumers	In-house	3
Producers	2	Contribution and explanation of products at the event	External	N/A
Organizers	2	Contact with the market, producers, and consumers	In-house	2

2.4 Event material

The material used to promote the event is shown and described below. Templates developed by the agroBRIDGES project have been used for dissemination on social networks such as LinkedIn and Twitter. In addition to the material for dissemination on social networks, a roll-up has been used for the market (Figure 6), as well as informative brochures.

For this event, a magnetic board has been designed with the agroBRIDGES logo to write “the list of local products that you need” as a gift to the attendees, moreover, a QR code with the link to the agroBRIDGES website has been included in the magnetic board.

In order to encourage the participation of those attending the market, a raffle was held with a basket of products offered by both producers and which had been tasted throughout the market (Figure 7).

Figure 4: Producer event social media graphic

Figure 5: Producer event social media graphic

Figure 6: Roll-up

Figure 7: Raffle basket

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

Following the decision to organise a Producer Event, it was identified that producers themselves, who could present their products at a local market, and producers who usually go to such markets in search of specific products and who might not know these producers, might be interested.

Regarding the producers who participated in the event, they were very interested, considering it a great opportunity to promote their products and to have a direct contact with consumers. In addition to the direct advantages of presenting their products, they appreciated the opportunity to exchange ideas with other producers in the same situation, to discuss what works and what doesn't, to discuss their business models and experiences, and to exchange contacts for medium- to long-term collaboration.

On the market side, they found it a very enriching experience, a new way to promote and make their market visible and to learn about the agroBRIDGES initiative and the scope of the project. Finally, with regard to consumers, the dissemination tasks on social networks by the organisers and the organisers by agroBRIDGES have been very successful and have helped to increase the number of attendees at this edition of the market. More information is provided in the following section.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

As previously mentioned, dissemination activities in social networks, among stakeholders and with support from the market organization, have been fundamental to ensure the success of the event.

The first publications in networks were made in December 2022, before Christmas, although the main dissemination activity was carried out during the month of January. The main diffusion on Twitter started about 20 days before the event, through publications in English and Spanish. At the same time, publications were also published on LinkedIn. In addition to the posts prior to the event, on the same day, January 28th, a new post was made on Twitter with images of the market, and afterwards, an article was written in the CTA website in both English and Spanish. Some examples of the publications are shown in Figures 8, 9 and 10.

Figure 8: Twitter post in Spanish

Figure 9: Twitter post in English

Figure 10: LinkedIn post in Spanish

Figure 11: Twitter post in English

Figure 12: Article in Spanish published on the website

viernes, 03 de febrero de 2023

CTA participa en un evento de productores locales del proyecto europeo AgroBRIDGES

La consultoras de Innovación María Jiménez y Paula Rosa participaron el pasado sábado 28 de enero en un evento de productores locales del proyecto europeo **AgroBRIDGES** [<https://www.agrobridges.eu/>] en el Mercado Agroecológico de San Jerónimo de Sevilla.

Durante el evento, se ha dado a conocer el proyecto AgroBRIDGES y a dos productores locales que participan en el proyecto: Grupo La Caña y Conservas contigo.

Este proyecto propone el desarrollo de un marco que incluya a distintas partes interesadas del sector agroalimentario, así como un conjunto de herramientas prácticas de apoyo para mejorar la posición de los agricultores dentro del mercado y reducir el margen de los intermediarios.

AgroBRIDGES está financiado por el programa de investigación e innovación Horizonte 2020 de la Unión Europea.

Conoce el proyecto AgroBRIDGES en 1 minuto en este vídeo>> [<https://youtu.be/HASukWBPdW>]

Algunas imágenes del evento

Figure 13: Article in English published on the website

Friday, 03 de February de 2023

CTA participates in an event for local producers of the European project AgroBRIDGES

Innovation consultants María Jiménez and Paula Rosa participated last Saturday, January 28, in an event for local producers of the European project **AgroBRIDGES** [<https://www.agrobridges.eu/>] in the Agroecological Market of San Jerónimo in Sevilla.

During the event, the AgroBRIDGES project and two local producers who participate in the project were made known: Grupo La Caña and Conservas contigo.

This project proposes the development of a framework that includes different stakeholders of the agri-food sector, as well as a set of practical support tools to improve the position of farmers within the market and reduce the margin of intermediaries.

AgroBRIDGES is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Get to know the AgroBRIDGES project in 1 minute in this video>> [<https://youtu.be/HASukWBPdW>]

Some pictures of the event

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Below photographs taken during the event are shown, in them you can see some of the consumers and producers who participated in our stand, both to taste the products and to learn about the project and why we were there.

In general, the public had a very good attitude, the attendees tasted the products while the origin of each of them was explained to them, they were very satisfied and very interested in knowing where they can buy these products in the city. In turn, the producers were delighted to be able to publicize their products and see consumers enjoying them. The moment of the basket draw was a long-awaited and fun moment for everyone.

Figure 14: Event implementation

Figure 15: Event implementation

Figure 16: Event implementation

Figure 17: Event implementation

Figure 18: Event implementation

Figure 19: Event implementation

3.2 Event participation

We consider 2 participating producers and 57 consumers, who were the ones who completed the questionnaire, however, at least 10 more producers visited the stand to exchange views with agroBRIDGES producers, and more than 100 consumers in total.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	2
Consumers	57
Total	59

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question						
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	Yes		No		Not Sure	
	31		4		22	
Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	Very informative	Relatively Informative	Neutral	Not Informative	Not Informative at all	No answer
	42	10	3	2	0	0
Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local producers, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	No answer
	40	14	2	1	0	0
Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local producers' food, various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	No answer
	37	18	2	0	0	0
Did you find enough information about how and where to buy local food from the producers or other businesses you've met?	Enough and very precise information	Enough information but I would need more details	Enough information but I need to search further on my own	Not enough information	No information at all	No answer
	33	17	6	1	0	0
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	No answer
	44	8	1	4	0	0
Total	196	67	14	8	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner.

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

Yes, these concepts help to be clear about the objective of the event.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, I would do the same event again because it has been a very positive experience for both producers, consumers and organizers. The only change would perhaps increase the number of producers participating.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, the guidelines have been very useful to have the templates to fill in with the data of the event, especially for dissemination on social networks.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, the instructions were clear, and it was enough.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Totally flexible, although the key aspects were clear and the objective of the event was clear, there was freedom to give a particular approach to the event.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

The fact that event attendees must fill out forms or give some type of information is always complicated, especially if the questionnaire must be filled in physically and several questions have to be answered. In addition, in some cases, the type of audience had certain limitations when reading the questions, as in the case of elderly people who could not read them correctly.

4.1.4 *Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines*

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the instructions are flexible and allow you to customize the event.

5. Conclusions

This event has allowed consumers to become familiar with the concept of short food supply chain, learn about the agroBRIDGES project, and increase their knowledge of local products and the advantages they offer compared to other products sold in large supermarkets or exported.

In the case of the invited producers, it has allowed them to have direct contact with consumers interested in products such as those they offer, while interacting with other local producers and the organic sector.

Not only has the event been of interest prior to and during the event, but some producers have requested more information on how it was organised and are considering possibilities to participate in the market following the model presented in the agroBRIDGES project.

In a nutshell, it has been a very enriching and rewarding experience for both the market organizers and the project organizers.